

	Code	Level of Education	Area	DataScientist Experi	Expererience with AI	Work in innovation projects	Number of projec	Fuction	Do you consider yourself experienced i identifying problems i projects?			
	P1	Bachelor's degree in progress	Proction Engineering	Up to 1 year	Work with supervision	Yes	2	Scrum Master, D	Partially agree			
	P2	PhD in progress	Physics	From 2 to 4 years	Work with supervision	Yes	6	Developer and S	Partially agree			
	P3	PhD in progress	Physics	More than 4 years	Work without supervision	Yes	5	data scientist, Sc	Partially agree			
	P4	Bachelor's degree in progress	Computer Engineering	Up to 1 year	Work without supervision	Yes	4	Developer e PO	Totally disagree			
	P5	Bachelor's degree in progress	Computer Engineering	Up to 1 year	Work without supervision	Yes	2	Developer	Partially agree			
	P6	Bachelor's degree in progress	Computer Engineering	From 2 to 4 years	Work without supervision	Yes	4	Developer e cien	Totally agree			
	P7	Bachelor's degree in progress	Computer Engineering	Up to 1 year	Work without supervision	Yes	4	Developer	Partially agree			
	P8	Bachelor's degree in progress	Computer Science	From 1 to 2 years	Work without supervision	Yes	2	Developer, Cient	Neutral			
	P9	Bachelor's degree in progress	Computer Engineering	Up to 1 year	Work without supervision	Yes	2	Developer	Partially dissagree			
	P10	Bachelor's degree in progress	Software Engineering	Up to 1 year	Work with supervision	Yes	4	Developer and sc	Neutral			